

Kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of some α -hydroxy acids by quinolinium bromochromate

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Manuscript received 22 April 2002, accepted 12 July 2002

The oxidation of glycollic, lactic, malic and a few substituted mandelic acids by quinolinium bromochromate (QBC) in dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) leads to the formation of the corresponding oxoacids. The reaction is first order each in QBC and the hydroxy acids. The reaction is catalyzed by the hydrogen ions. The hydrogen ion dependence has the form $k_{\text{obs}} = a + b [\text{H}^+]$. Oxidation of mandelic acid has been studied in different organic solvents. The solvent effect has been analyzed by using Kamlet's and Swain's multiparametric equations. A mechanism involving a hydride ion transfer via a chromate ester is proposed.

Quinolinium bromochromate (QBC) has been used as a mild and selective oxidizing reagent in synthetic organic chemistry¹. There seems to be no reports on the kinetic and mechanistic aspects of oxidation reactions by QBC. We have been interested in the kinetics of reactions of complexed Cr^{VI} species and have already reported kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of some α -hydroxy acids by other pyridinium and quinolinium halochromates²⁻⁴. Hydroxy acids may be oxidized either as alcohols, yielding the corresponding oxoacids⁵ or may undergo oxidative decarboxylation to yield a ketone⁶. There seems to be no report on the oxidation of α -hydroxy acids by QBC. In continuation of our earlier work with halochromates, we now report the kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of some hydroxy acids by QBC in DMSO as solvent. A suitable mechanism has also been proposed.

Results and Discussion

The rate and other experimental data were obtained for all the hydroxy acids studied. Since the results were similar, only representative data are reproduced here.

The oxidation of hydroxy acids resulted in the formation of the corresponding oxoacids. Product analysis and stoichiometric determinations indicate that the overall reaction may be written as

QBC undergoes a two-electron change. This is in accord with our earlier observations with other halochromates^{7,8}.

Rate-laws : The reactions were found to be first order in QBC. The individual kinetic runs are strictly first order in QBC. Further, the pseudo-first order rate constant does not

depend on the initial [QBC]. The reaction increases linearly with an increase in the [hydroxy acid] (Table 1).

The oxidation of hydroxy acids by QBC in an atmosphere of nitrogen failed to induce the polymerization of acrylonitrile. Further, an addition of acrylonitrile had no effect on the rate (Table 1).

Table 1. Rate constant for the oxidation of mandelic acids by QBC* at 303 K

10^3 [QBC] mol dm ⁻³	[IIA] mol dm ⁻³	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ s ⁻¹
1 00	0 10	2 02
1 00	0 20	3 90
1 00	0 40	7 85
1 00	0 60	11 7
1 00	0 80	15 6
1 00	1 00	19 7
1 00	2 00	40 2
2 00	0 20	3 86
4 00	0 20	3 94
6 00	0 20	3 98
8 00	0 20	3 82
1 00	0 40	7 92*

* Contained 0 001 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile

Effect of hydrogen ions : The reaction is catalyzed by hydrogen ions. The hydrogen ion dependence has the form (Table 2) :

$$k_{\text{obs}} = a + b [\text{H}^+] \quad (2)$$

The values of a and b , for mandelic acids, are $1.97 \pm 0.06 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $3.51 \pm 0.10 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$, respectively

Table 2. Effect of hydrogen ion concentration on the oxidation of mandelic acid by QBC[QBC] = 0.001 mol dm⁻³, [Mandelic acid] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³, temp. = 303 K

[H ⁺]	0.10	0.20	0.40	0.60	0.80	1.00
104 k_{obs}/s^{-1}	23.1	27.2	34.1	39.5	48.6	54.8

 $(r^2 = 0.9965)$.

Kinetic isotope effect : To ascertain the importance of the cleavage of the C–H bond in the rate-determining step, the oxidation of α -deuterioformic acid (DMA) was studied. The results show the presence of a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect (Table 3). The value of $k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}}$ is 5.44 at 303 K. The oxidation of mandelic acids was studied in 95%

3). The entropy and enthalpy of activation of the ten substituted mandelic acids are linearly related ($r = 0.9985$). The value of isokinetic temperature evaluated^{9,10} from this plot is 1213 ± 45 K. The correlation was tested and found genuine by using Exner's criterion¹¹. A linear isokinetic relationship is necessary condition for the validity of linear free energy relationship, which suggests that all the hydroxy acids are oxidized by the same mechanism.

The observed H⁺ dependence suggests that the reaction follows two mechanistic pathways, one acid-independent and the other acid-dependent. The acid-catalysis may well be attributed to a protonation of QBC to give a stronger oxidant and electrophile,

Table 3. Rate constants and activation parameters for the oxidation of hydroxy acids by QBC

R	10 ⁴ $k_2 / (\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1})$				ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹
	293	303	313	323 K			
H	9.31	19.7	42.4	88.2	56.5 ± 0.7	-111 ± 2	89.4 ± 0.6
<i>p</i> -F	13.1	27.2	57.3	112	54.0 ± 0.4	-116 ± 1	88.5 ± 0.3
<i>p</i> -Cl	5.52	11.8	26.2	57.2	58.9 ± 1.0	-107 ± 3	90.6 ± 0.8
<i>p</i> -Br	4.51	10.3	22.8	48.3	59.7 ± 0.2	-106 ± 1	91.1 ± 0.2
<i>p</i> -Me	41.6	78.8	152	288	48.3 ± 0.7	-126 ± 2	85.8 ± 0.6
<i>p</i> -Pr ⁱ	35.1	66.6	141	262	50.8 ± 1.0	-119 ± 3	86.2 ± 0.8
<i>p</i> -OMe	387	640	1110	1820	38.3 ± 0.6	-142 ± 2	80.4 ± 0.5
<i>m</i> -Cl	1.55	3.80	9.06	20.5	65.3 ± 0.3	-96 ± 1	93.6 ± 0.3
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	0.31	0.83	2.17	5.48	72.8 ± 0.6	-83 ± 2	97.5 ± 0.5
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	0.22	0.61	1.62	4.17	74.6 ± 0.4	-87 ± 1	98.3 ± 0.4
GA	3.38	6.27	11.8	22.7	47.4 ± 0.9	-150 ± 3	92.0 ± 0.8
LA	6.27	12.5	24.2	47.1	50.2 ± 0.5	-135 ± 2	90.4 ± 0.4
MLA	5.11	9.62	18.3	34.2	47.4 ± 0.6	-147 ± 2	91.0 ± 0.5
DMA	1.66	3.62	8.10	17.5	59.4 ± 0.8	-115 ± 3	93.6 ± 0.6
$k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}}$	5.61	5.44	5.23	5.04			

deuterium oxide under identical conditions. The results show the absence of a solvent isotope effect.

Effect of solvents : The rate of oxidation of mandelic acid was determined in nineteen different organic solvents. The choice of the solvents was limited by the solubility of QBC and reaction with primary and secondary alcohols. There was no noticeable reaction with the solvents chosen. The kinetics are similar in all the solvents. The values of k_2 at 303 K are recorded in Table 4.

Effect of temperature : The rates of oxidation of all the hydroxy acids were determined at four different temperatures and the activation parameters were calculated (Table

The rate constants of oxidation, k_2 in eighteen solvents (CS₂ was not considered, as the complete range of solvent parameters was not available) were correlated in terms of the linear solvation energy relationship (4) of Kamlet *et al.*¹²,

$$\log k_2 = A_0 + p\pi^* + b\beta + a\alpha \quad (4)$$

In this equation, π^* represents the solvent polarity, β the hydrogen bond acceptor basicities, α the hydrogen bond donor acidity and A_0 the intercept term. It may be mentioned here that out of the 18 solvents, 12 have a value of zero for α . The results of correlation analyses in terms of (4), a biparametric equation involving π^* and β , and separately with π^* and β are given in eqns. (5–8),

Table 4. Effect of solvents on the oxidation of *p*-methylmandelic acid by QBC at 303 K

Solvent	$10^4 k_2$ $\text{dm}^{-3} \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$	Solvent	$10^4 k_2$ $\text{dm}^{-3} \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$
Chloroform	20.4	Toluene	6.31
1, 2-Dichloroethane	24.0	Acetophenone	35.5
Dichloromethane	26.3	THF	11.2
DMSO	78.8	t-Butanol	9.55
Acetone	21.4	1,4-Dioxane	11.7
DMF	42.7	1,2-Dimethoxyethane	6.92
Butanone	16.2	Carbon disulfide	3.63
Nitrobenzene	31.0	Acetic acid	3.98
Benzene	7.94	Ethyl acetate	10.2
Cyclohexane	0.79		

Table 5. Temperature dependence of the reaction constant

Para- meter	293	303	313	323 K
ρ^*	-2.08 ± 0.01	-1.93 ± 0.02	-1.82 ± 0.01	-1.69 ± 0.02
r^2	0.9999	0.9989	0.9998	0.9999
sd	0.005	0.007	0.007	0.005

$$\log k_2 = -4.11 + (1.64 \pm 0.19)\pi^* + (0.23 \pm 0.16)\beta - (0.16 \pm 0.15)\alpha \quad (5)$$

$$R^2 = 0.8735; \text{sd} = 0.17; n = 8; \Psi = 0.28$$

$$\log k_2 = -4.04 + (1.70 \pm 0.18)\pi^* + (1.78 \pm 0.15)\beta \quad (6)$$

$$R^2 = 0.8637; \text{sd} = 0.18; \Psi = 0.29$$

$$\log k_2 = -4.01 + (1.74 \pm 0.18)\pi^* \quad (7)$$

$$r^2 = 0.8512; \text{sd} = 0.18; n = 18; \Psi = 0.29$$

$$\log k_2 = -3.05 + (0.48 \pm 0.37)\beta \quad (8)$$

$$r^2 = 0.0966; \text{sd} = 0.44; n = 18; \Psi = 0.85$$

Here n is the number of data points and Ψ the Exner's statistical parameter¹³.

Kamlet's triparametric equation¹² explains *ca.* 87% of the effect of solvent on the oxidation. However, by Exner's criterion the correlation is not even satisfactory (*cf.* eqn. 8). The major contribution is of solvent polarity. It alone accounts for *ca.* 85% of the data. Both β and α play relatively minor roles.

The data on the solvent effect were analyzed in terms of Swain's equation¹⁴ of cation- and anion-solvating concept of the solvents also

$$\log k_2 = aA + bB + C \quad (9)$$

here A and B represents the anion-solvating power and cat-

ion-solvating power of the solvent respectively, and C is the intercept term. ($A + B$) is postulated to represent the solvent polarity. The rates in different solvents were analyzed in terms of eqn. (9), separately with A and B and with ($A + B$),

$$\log k_2 = (0.63 \pm 0.04)A + (1.74 \pm 0.03)B - 4.20 \quad (10)$$

$$R^2 = 0.9961; \text{sd} = 0.03; n = 19; \Psi = 0.05$$

$$\log k_2 = 0.38(\pm 0.58)A - 3.01 \quad (11)$$

$$r^2 = 0.4652; \text{sd} = 0.47; n = 19; \Psi = 0.99$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.70(\pm 0.11)B - 4.03 \quad (12)$$

$$r^2 = 0.9290; \text{sd} = 0.13; n = 19; \Psi = 0.19$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.37 \pm 0.14 (A + B) - 4.17 \quad (13)$$

$$r^2 = 0.8414; \text{sd} = 0.19; n = 19; \Psi = 0.29$$

The rates of oxidation of *p*-methylmandelic acid in different solvents show an excellent correlation in Swain's equation (*cf.* (9)) with the cation-solvating power playing the major role. In fact, the cation-solvation alone accounts for *ca.* 99% of the data. The correlation with the anion-solvating power is very poor. The solvent polarity, represented by ($A + B$), also accounts for *ca.* 84% of the data. In view of the fact that solvent polarity is able to account for *ca.* 84% of the data, an attempt was made to correlate the rate with the relative permittivity of the solvent. However, a plot of $\log k_2$ against the inverse of the relative permittivity is not linear ($r^2 = 0.5405$; $\text{sd} = 0.32$; $\Psi = 0.53$).

Mechanisms :

Absence of any effect of added acrylonitrile on the reaction discounts the possibility of a one-electron oxidation, leading to the formation of free radicals. The presence of a substantial kinetic isotope effect in the oxidation of mandelic acid^{4,15} confirms the cleavage of the α -C-H bond in the rate-determining step. The large negative reaction constant together with the excellent correlation with Brown's σ^+ values¹⁶ points to a highly electron-deficient carbon centre in the transition state. The transition state thus approaches a carbocation in character. This is supported by the solvent effect also. Greater role played by the cation-solvating power of the solvents supports the postulation of a carbocationic transition state. Therefore, the correlation analysis of substituent and solvent effects on the oxidation of mandelic acid support the mechanism involving a hydride-ion transfer via chromate ester.

Kwart and Nickle¹⁷ showed that a study of the dependence of the kinetic isotope effect on temperature can gainfully employed to solve this problem. The data for protio- and deuteriomandelic acids, fitted to the familiar expres-

sion, $k_H/k_D = A_H/A_D \exp(E_a/RT)$ ^{18,19} show a direct correspondence with the properties of a symmetrical transition state in which the activation energy difference (E_a) for k_H/k_D is equal to the zero-point energy difference for the respective C-H and C-D bonds ($\approx 4.5 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$) and the frequency factors and the entropies of activation of the respective reactions are nearly equal. Similar phenomena were observed earlier in the oxidation of diols by BPCC²⁰ and that of hydroxy acids by PFC^{4,15}.

Bordwell²¹ documented a very cogent evidence against the occurrence of concerted one-step bimolecular processes by hydrogen transfer and it is evident that in the present studies also the hydrogen transfer does not occur by an acyclic bimolecular process. It is well established that intrinsically concerted sigmatropic reactions, characterized by transfer of hydrogen in a cyclic transition state, are the only truly symmetrical processes involving a linear hydrogen transfer²². Littler²³ also showed that a cyclic hydride transfer, in the oxidation of alcohols by Cr^{VI} , involves six electrons and, being a Hückle-type system, is an allowed process. Thus the overall mechanism is proposed to involve the formation of a chromate ester in fast pre-equilibrium and then a decomposition of the ester in a subsequent slow step via a cyclic concerted symmetrical transition state leading to the product (Scheme 1). The observed negative value of entropy of activation also supports a polar transition state.

Scheme 1

The observed negative entropy of activation also supports it. As the charge separation takes place, the charged ends become highly solvated. This results in an immobilization of a large number of solvent molecules, reflected in the loss of entropy²⁴.

It is of interest to compare the mode of oxidation of hydroxy acids by PCC²⁵, PFC⁴ and QBC. The oxidation by PFC exhibited Michaelis-Menten type kinetics with respect to hydroxy acids. While the oxidations by PCC and QBC present a similar kinetic picture. The rate laws, hydrogen ion dependence and kinetic isotope effect are similar in both

the cases. In the oxidations by PFC and QBC, excellent correlations were obtained in terms of Swain's equation with the cation solvating power of the solvents playing the major role. In all the three oxidations the polar reactions are negative.

Experimental

The hydroxy acids were commercial products of the highest purity available and used as such. The preparation and specification of the substituted mandelic acids have been described earlier²⁶. QBC was prepared by reported method¹ and its purity was checked by iodometric method. α -Deuteriomandelic acid ($\text{PhCD}(\text{OH})\text{COOH}$ or DMA) was prepared by the reported method²⁷ and its isotopic purity (ascertained by NMR spectra) was $94 \pm 5\%$. Due to the non-aqueous nature of the solvent, toluene *p*-sulfonic acid TsOH was used as a source of hydrogen ions. Solvents were purified by the usual method²⁸.

Product analyses were carried out under kinetic conditions, i.e. with an excess of the reductant over QBC. In a typical experiment, a mixture of mandelic acid (7.6 g, 0.05 mol) and QBC (3.10 g, 0.01 mol) dissolved in DMSO (100 ml) was allowed to stand in dark for ≈ 24 h to ensure the completion of the reaction. It was then treated with an excess (250 ml) of a freshly prepared saturated solution of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine in 2 mol dm^{-3} HCl and kept overnight in a refrigerator. The precipitated 2,4-dinitrophenyl-hydrazone (DNP) was filtered off, dried, weighed, crystallized from ethanol. The product was identical (m.p. and m.m.p.) to an authentic sample of DNP of phenylglyoxylic acid. Similar experiments with the other hydroxy acids yielded the DNP of the corresponding oxoacids (78–89% yields) after crystallization. The oxidation state of chromium in completely reduced reaction mixtures, determined by an iodometric method, was 3.96 ± 0.15 .

Kinetic measurements : The pseudo-first order conditions were attained by keeping excess ($\times 15$ or greater) of the hydroxy acid over QBC. The temperature was kept constant to ± 0.1 K. The solvent was DMSO, unless specified otherwise. The reaction were followed by monitoring the decrease in the concentration of QBC spectrophotometrically at 356 nm for up to 80% of the reaction. No other reactant or product had any significant absorption at this wavelength. The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) were computed from the linear least-square plots of $\log [\text{QBC}]$ vs time. Duplicate kinetic runs showed that the rates were reproducible within $\pm 3\%$. The second order rate constants (k_2) were calculated from the relation : $k_2 = k_{\text{obs}}/[\text{hydroxy acid}]$. All experiments, other than those for studying the ef-

fect of hydrogen ions, were carried out in the absence of TsOH

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial support

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